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We dedicate this work to our loving Parents and kind teachers. . .

Declaration

This thesis concludes Master's studies at the Halmstad University. The topic of research was self defined considering our background in games development and studies in digital forensics area. Its intended audience includes R&D teams of gaming companies and developers who develop blockchain based multiplayer online video games and enthusiasts who are interested in this particular area of research and development.

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Abstract

Video gaming has always been a blooming industry. With the emergence of online multiplayer video games, this industry's worth has sky rocketed. Online multiplayer video games store data of player's credentials, in-game progress, in-game virtual assets and payment details etc. Which mean security threats to these systems are nothing new and securing these games have always meant to protect player's data from unauthorized breach.

Integration of Blockchain technology in online multiplayer video games apart from other amazing features, provides a way to prove digital ownership of virtual assets with their verifiable scarcity. Trade of these in-game virtual assets have always been a goal for online multiplayer gaming companies, but there was none enough trust-able infrastructure available which can be relied on. Blockchain just solved that problem. It provided a platform for these asset's secure and transparent transaction between players.

Topic for our research not only consider the security challenges in online games but specifically blockchain based online multiplayer games. This adaptation is still new and there is need of consideration of new security challenges. In this dissertation we try to bring out some important challenges related to security of blockchain based online multiplayer video games. There are currently no studies around security concerns and challenges of the integration of the online multiplayer video games in the emerging blockchain systems. In order to fill in the gap, this dissertation discusses and identifies two main security concerning questions related to this domain. Also this dissertation provides basic steps for expanding future research and application in this joint domain.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Main Topic

Video games are played by millions of people around the globe and video gaming industry apart from being entertainment and recreational industry, is also a multi-billion dollars industry, [3]. Online games attract more audience because people get a chance to compete against each other and it provide more fun than solo games. Additionally online games provide integrated function to the players, including user registering, interaction, long-term data preserving and other kinds of value-added services, [4]. When many people are involved in a product and want to outdo each other, there is always a chance of suspicious activities to win the game by illicit means. As no real life competition is ever free from cheating concerns or threats, similarly multiplayer online video games also face these threats. This deduces that most cyber security threats to online video games are related to cheating players who are either able to hack the system or DDoS attacks to the server. Topic for our research not only consider the security challenges in online games but specifically blockchain based multiplayer online games. Technology of blockchain allows games developers and companies to incentivize their in-game virtual assets. According to [5] "Almost all types of online multiplayer games provide some mechanism for players to exchange virtual items or game currency. Furthermore most, if not all, massively multiplayer online games also provide the ability to auction virtual items to other players." Integration of Blockchain in these games apart from other amazing features, provides a way to prove digital ownership of virtual assets with their verifiable scarcity. This adaptation is still new and there is need of consideration around new security challenges. In this dissertation we try to bring out some important challenges related to security of blockchain based multiplayer online video games.

1.2 Keywords

Multiplayer Online Video Games, Blockchain, Blockchain based online video games, security threats to online video games, security challenges in blockchain based online games, Cyber Security Issues in blockchain based online multiplayer video games

1.3 Problem Description

Security challenges in blockchain based online video games are considered to be cheating related or DDos attacks or hacking the console etc. But with the new trend of blockchain based products, when video gaming is adopted with this technology there are many aspects left to explore. One issue is related to games developers such as what challenges they are facing? How they have to adopt their development process? what steps they need to take? What issues they need to consider before developing such games? This makes up the first question of our research work. Other issue is exactly how secure these kind of games are now? There sure are some benefits of integrating blockchain with video games but does this solve all the security problems? Because blockchain technology brings security in terms of ownership of assets and their trade but online games themselves has potential to be hacked or being tempered with. In traditional online video game, if it is hacked, it does not cause monetary harm. Only effect is inside the game environment but with incentivize items, this will make it more cumbersome offense than it was previously with traditional online games. These two issues make up our research questions which are related to security of blockchain based online video games and challenges the games developers are facing if they adopt blockchain technology.

1.4 Motivation and Contribution

Being games developers ourselves and students of digital forensics, bringing these two fields close seems like a responsibility rather than educational work. These two fields are kept apart as criminal offence in video gaming industry is never weighted as much as it should be. This research work will close the gap and will provide room for more discussion around conjunction of both of these fields.

1.5 Research Question

1. What challenges (in term of cyber security) games developer face if they shift to blockcahin based online games?
2. Possible cyber security concerns with blockchain based multiplayer online games?

1.6 Thesis Structure

Chapter 2 details background knowledge required to understand the area of research work. We discussed the main types of Video Games including our targeted games type, their architecture and security threats related to them.

Chapter 3 Provides a little detail on what blockchain based online games are and some of their pros and cons and their limitation.

Chapter 4 presents our research method to answer the research questions

Chapter 5 contains detail about our experiment to better understand the research questions at hand and their results

Chapter 6 presents the evaluation of our experiment, main findings of the thesis and discussion around this topic.

Chapter 7 concludes the dissertation and details the possible future work that can be done to further research in this particular area.

Chapter 2

Background

2.1 Cyber Security and Cyber Security Threats

Cyber assets are comprised of system including hardware and software, communication network and data[6]. Any malicious attempt to breach these assets is called cyber attack. Cyber attacks are performed to gain benefits through illicit means and are major threats to organizations with valuable information system. Possibility of any kind of organized attacks or breaches in information system either by human error or accidental breach are defined as cyber security threats.

Cyber security aims at providing protection of cyber assets from these cyber attacks. According to [7], "Cyber security consists of technologies, processes and controls that are designed to protect systems, networks and data from cyber attacks". It also states that effective cyber security reduces the risk of cyber attacks.

2.2 Video Games

Electronic games are often called computer games or video games. In this dissertation we have used term video game as it has more generalized meaning. Video games have been around since the very first video game made in 1958 by a physicist "William Higinbotham" [8]. Computer games or video games also refer to electronic games that have user interaction through respective input systems and output through a screen display.

Video games are major computer applications and are big part of digital entertainment industry. Since fifties, video games have gone through different phases depending upon the inventions in technologies.

Types Of Video Games

Video games can be divided into different categories depending upon the technologies they were being built and played on, referred to as platform and the type of game play i.e. the logic of the game play. Platform is the combination of hardware and software which allows the video game to operate [9].

2.2.1 Based on Platform

With the invention of different technologies throughout the history, there came several kind of games that were dependent on their respective platform, on which these were made and played on.

Early Mainframe Games Most earliest video game were mainframe games because they were played on mainframe computers and were mainly played by researchers and computer specialists [9].

Arcade Games These games are truly electronic games rather than computer games. Arcade games are played on special coin operated machines that unlike a computer system can perform no other task than playing the game. These special coin operated machines were designed to solely play the video games and mainly had hard wired state machine built from logical gates and counters.

Console Games Unlike arcade games machines, special consoles were invented that can be attached to ordinary television set at home to play games. Game consoles came with replaceable cartridges to variety of games

PC games With the invention of personal computers including TRS-80 and Apple I in 1976, personal computer games came into existence.

Mobile games Mobile games can be easily separated from PC or console games in terms of input and interaction involved. With iOS, Android and other high standard operating systems for mobile devices, there are new options available for interaction with user such as global positioning information, camera device and touch screen, which was not possible in traditional PC or console games.

Virtual Reality games Virtual reality based games are buzz word right now. A special head mounted unit provides stereoscopic screens and motion tracking to display virtual environment that responds with head movement of player. Now a days some advance

VR systems include eye tracking with which movement of eyes could be used to navigate in the environment same as in real life and special control units for hands to provide interaction with virtual environment through touch of hands. As a whole, all this equipment makes it as real life like experience as possible for players.

Online Games These are played on PC or consoles but platform here changes in terms of network. These are played over internet. Most PC games were single player games and were played with or against the game software. With the commercialization of internet, era of online gaming came into existence. Online games are played by one or more persons over the internet on their respective devices i.e game console, PC computer or mobile phones.

2.2.2 Solo Vs Multiplayer Games

Video games can be divided into two basic categories based on number of real players involved which are solo and multiplayer video games.

Solo or Single Player Video Games As basic video games are single player or solo games. Which means a single player is playing game either with the game play software or against it. In strategy based games it is sometimes called AI. A solo game can be either online or offline depending upon its provider and game play.

Offline solo games are simply played on respective platform console, arcade, PC or mobile etc. These are played with or against AI designed within the game play software

Online solo games are installed as client on its respective platform and is being updated from server. It is still played with or against AI of game play which runs on server part.

Multiplayer Video Games A major twist in gaming industry was seen when multiplayer games came into existence. That is when player can play with or against each other. This makes the game more interesting for players and more dynamic output from the game can be generated. Although solo games are played all around the world but multiplayers games are more revenue generating and are more popular. According to [10] Multiplayer games come in three categories.

Turn Based Multiplayers Game This was the most initial phase of multiplayer gaming history. In turn based each player takes their turn at the game play either like a chess game with one step at a time or like a racing game by playing whole level at

Table 2.1 General Online Multiplayer Games Types [1]

Type	Number of Players	Description
FPS	≤ 256	First Person Shooter
RTS	≤ 8	Real-Time Strategy Games
MMO	Thousands	Massively Multiplayer Online
MMORPG	Thousands	Massively Multiplayer Online Role-Playing Games
MMORTS	Thousands	Massively Multiplayer Online Real-Time Strategy Games
MMOFPS	Hundreds to Thousands	Massively Multiplayer Online First Person Shooter
MOBA	Hundreds to Thousands	Multiplayer Online Battle Arena
Sandbox	Hundreds	Multiplayer Sandbox
MMOS	Hundreds to Thousands	Massively Multiplayer Online Sandbox

each turn and results can be produced based on each players performance. These are still played in online duo compition styled games such as tennis, badminton etc.

Split Screen Multiplayers Game These games are perfect for category that account for input at runtime such as racing or survival game. Each player sees their own character on their part of screen and are competing in the same level. The one to reach goal at first wins. This way both players compete at same time with or against each other. In survival type, each player sees a hologram of their partner or opponent.

Online Multiplayers In this type players can be playing from different sides of planet and competing with each other. Thanks to the technology of internet, these games are played over the internet and number of players can be hundreds to thousand depending upon the gameplay. Our focus of the research is on online multiplayer games. Furthermore [1] there are different types of online multiplayer games represented in the table below.

2.3 Achitecture of Online Multiplayer Games

As with any online application, servers plays an important role in online multiplayer game. All the core game logic is built mainly inside the server and players connect with server through client application on their respective platforms via internet. There are two main architectures for server based games [11]

Remote-server Game As the name suggests, client application of game runs on player's machine (any platform) and gameplay is offered via remote server. The application

connects over a network to the server. Each player's client application/game communicates with server separately and server is responsible for receiving all player's actions and running a game logic, computing the results based on each player's input and presenting the updated game states to all the players. This is also called hub and spoke configurations [12]. These games hold more players, up to hundred and thousands of players.

Peer-to-peer Game In peer to peer architecture there is no remote server. All player's devices connect with each other via Bluetooth, infrared or Wi-Fi and game application on each system sends and receives data to and from each connected player. Game logic is built on each game application and each device is remained syn with others to produce results of the game play in accordance to each player's input. These games are mostly played in between few players who are physically in a close distance to each other.

2.4 Cyber Security Threats in Online Multiplayer Games

In a solo game there is no other person interested in the progress of a player other than player himself. At most if the game is online, players need to secure their password to the application which can be retrieved in case it gets hacked or forgotten. In online multiplayer games, many players are competing with each other and each player tries to get ahead of their opponent. This competitive environment gives rise to many illicit activities in order to get advance in game play. Specifically in online gaming there are some factors which can be abused in order to achieve this.

Virtual Items Virtual items are very valuable in a gameplay and mostly these items give leverage to one player over other. Collecting these items can be expensive or time consuming. There are many plugin software available to abuse the game logic and provide these items in a bulk. Plug-in software is a program that pre-designs the game behavior through the control of virtual characters in the game [4]. These plugins can help one player to get virtual items in bulk without paying for them or achieve them through game play or these can distort the items so that other players cannot achieve them. This form of cheating produces worst results for the gaming companies and they can lose their potential players and data.

Hacking Each player has their account with the gaming application in online multiplayer game. These accounts contain all the updated state of game play of a player. Many

viruses are deliberately made to attack these account to steal the password of player.

Trojans these Trojans are embedded with game application to record players input sequence. and password is stolen.

Man made hacking According to [4], attackers can pose as customer service staff to players and can ask for vital information of account such as user name etc. Some fraudsters can send some fake "official gifts" and other means to lure the player into a fishing website that is very similar to the game's official website. The fishing website can acquire information of the account and password from the user, so that the hacker can log into the account with the information obtained to transfer virtual assets, game currency etc, in order to sell these for real money offline.

Server Maintenance During server maintenance, some security threats can arise. As server need parameters in order to achieve normal access procedure. These parameters can be abused in order to hack or corrupt the gameplay logic in server.

2.5 Blockchain

By design, the blockchain is a decentralized Peer to Peer technology. [13]. Blockchain stores blocks of information that are identical across its network, so that it can not be controlled by any single entity and has no single point of failure.

Blockchain was mainly used to facilitate in cryptocurrency transactions but its uses have increased due to its inherent features like distributed data, cryptographic security, immutability, and infinitely expanding capacity[14] Its time that this technology is setting its foot into video gaming market and whole video gaming industry is taking new turn to accumulate with blockchain.

Chapter 3

Blockchain Based Online Video Games

Integration of blockchain technology and video gaming have opened up a new marketplace for virtual or digital in-game assets. When integrated with online gaming, blockchain technology adds a layers of security, fast and secure payment networks, a way to prove digital ownership of virtual assets with their verifiable scarcity, and an ability for developers to properly monetize their product [15].

According to [15], These virtual assets are non-fungible and verify-ably scarce. Thus these assets are token-ized and ownership of the token directly reflects ownership of the asset, immutably stored on the blockchain. The authenticity of these virtual assets is guaranteed using smart contracts standards such as the ERC-721 non-fungible token standard. One of the major issues with cryptocurrency is that there just aren't a lot of uses for it. [15] Cryptocurrency is a natural fit for games with micro-transactions, because it gives players the option to trade their hard-earned in-game currency outside of the game.

Table 3.1 A brief comparison between traditional online games and blockchain based online games [2]

Traditional Online games	Blockchain based online games
Assets are owned by the developer	Assets are owned by the player
Assets are transferable between games	Assets are inter-operable across games
Player history is hard to share between games	Personalized contents based on Player history

3.1 Benefits of Blockchain based Online Video Games

Many big companies such as Xbox and Sony wanted to allow players to purchase digital items through achievements points earned by playing the game [16]. But the idea never came to life because players can hack the accounts and can increase the achievement points. There is no way to distinguish between rightful player and hacker until unless physically seeing the console.

Blockchain just provided a secure way to achieve it. Each game would require to use digital currency and wallet for transactions based on the blockchain they use and all digital assets will hold a value and players and developers can monetize these assets.

Blockchain brings many other benefits to online video games. Some general benefits of blockchain technology integrated with video gaming are such as

Digital Market Place As discussed before, virtual assets/items in online video games can be tokenized or converted to decentralized cryptocurrency and can benefit both player and developers. These items can be sold via decentralized marketplace [17].

The problem with centralized economies like the Steam Community Market is that they don't allow the player to cash out. Instead, players have to use a middleman service like PayPal or eBay [18].

Security Online video games are mostly subjected to DDoS attack because of centralized networks that have a single-point-of-failure. On the contrary, video games based on blockchain technology are not vulnerable to DDoS attacks as these are decentralized and there is no single-point-of-failure. Additionally Blockchain cannot be cheated or tampered with because it is decentralized [18].

No dedicated Server For online video games, developers have to maintain a dedicated server. Expensive bandwidth or server cost can be reduced because blockchain is peer to peer [17].

Transparency [13] Blockchain can make game logic transparent as well.

For example in competitive gaming, the background gameplay logic is considered to be true and fair. Blockchain could create a public record of the game's logic. If one suspects the output of the match, the footage can be compared to the blockchain record to validate that there was no foul play [16].

3.2 Limitation of adopting Blockchain in Video Games

Alongside benefits of blockchain based gaming there are some limitations as well.

Scope of video games The biggest problem with gaming on the blockchain is speed. In a real-time multiplayer game, a simple action can trigger a cascade of state changes [18]. This would take a huge toll on the frame-rate as every single state change is verified on the blockchain. Thus its use is only restricted to turn-based strategy games where latency and frame-rate are not a factor.

Tokenization Every blockchain-based multiplayer game would need to have its own crypto currency system to incentivize the virtual assets. For example video games based on Ethereum use Ether and games based on Bitcoin blockchain use Bitcoins as cryptocurrency.

3.3 Recent Development

New games are being developed and launched which use blockchain technology in order to incentivize their virtual items. Also there are some platform being developed for indie games developers to tokenize their virtual assets so that these tokens can be used to incentivize the assets.

According to [16] some of the blockchain based games are as following,

Cryptokitties [19] is an Ethereum based game in which players collect and breed virtual cats. These virtual kitties are the assets which can be traded inside or outside the game.

Etheremon is a similar game, inspired by Pokémon [20] and based on Ethereum.

Lordmancer II is a blockchain-based, massively multiplayer online role-playing game (MMORPG) currently in beta for mobile.

EtherWarfare is a game based on Ethereum blockchain and hence uses Ether as digital currency. Players use their ethereum accounts for assets purchases etc.

Ether Quest [21] Similar to EtherWarfare, Ether Quest works through the Ethereum blockchain and uses Ether as an internal currency.

Spells of Genesis [22] uses Bitcoin's blockchain instead of Ethereum's.

Beyond the Void [23] was created for players interested in a Multiplayer Online Battle Arena (MOBA) strategy, a science-fiction game that runs on the Ethereum blockchain. [16] The developers of the game require all players to have an account set up on Mist, Ethereum's official wallet. While other blockchain-based games rely on browsers, Beyond the Void requires players to create an account on Steam and download the client to play the game.

Additionally there are some companies that provide tokens for games based on blockchain technology such as

ForceProtocol [24] aims to provide players within the online gaming space with anti-piracy protection, P2P trading, and an honorary reward system. It provides a digital market place as well to generate token against virtual assets. These tokens then can be used as cryptocurrency.

Chapter 4

Research Method

"Blockchain based online video games" is quite new field and not much research work has been done related to security concerns and challenges in this area. Although there is a lot of development going on in this field, so better suited method of this research work is search for all the related companies and all the new products being launched including blockchain based online multiplayer games as well as token based decentralized platforms for transactions of virtual items in video games.

4.1 Literature Review

For literature review we chose Google Scholar, IEEE Explore Digital Library and Science Direct. By following systematic approach to traditional literature review, we searched for research articles published around the field of security concerns in online video games and blockchain based video games. Some example keywords and search phrases for research articles topic were mostly

1. "blockchain applications"
2. "blockchain based online games"
3. "Security issues in online video games"
4. "Security issues in computer games"
5. "security concerns in blockchain technology"
6. "Cyber security threats in gaming"

Once we find some useful research papers, these helped to refine our keywords and search phases to retrieve most relevant information for example we found that most articles use similar keywords such as:

7. "Security Model of Online games"
8. "Security research of Massively Multiplayer Online Games"
9. "Peer to peer trading for Online Games"
10. "security and Privacy in Blockchain Environment"

Most of the topic we found were around security issues of online gaming and unfortunately no research paper was found on cyber security issues of blockchain based online games. There are several blogs and articles written by mostly developers or the developing companies which we cover in next section. Still these blogs and articles discuss technical details of embedding blockchain into video games and its pros and cons. But no security related work is seen in this context.

4.2 Online Gaming Blogs and Articles

Again most of the online blogs and articles are about new products in blockchain based online games and almost none are about security concerns in this area. Reason for such minimum concern is discussed as conclusion and result analysis in this dissertation. Once we found the most prominent companies working in this field. We read blogs and articles written by their research and development teams. We searched for almost all of the companies that are developing such games or platforms which facilitate the blockchain based games.

4.3 Search on latest developments

There is a lot of development going on in this field. We can gather a lot of information by just looking at the latest trends and development in this field. The type of games being developed and how they are changing the market trend with them.

We can also argue how much these new products are concerned with security related issues. Some companies are developing games of their own and at the same time there are companies which allow indie developers to submit their games and provide trading platform for all virtual items inside those games.

As our concern is related to security issues in this field and challenges that developers are

facing to adopt this technology. Some companies provide useful information on how secure they are making their platform and this serves good information related to cyber security of video games development.

XAYA [25] is one of such platform. Developers can submit their games and this environment provides blockchain based gaming solutions.

Tokenized Games [26] also provides blockchain based gaming solutions.

ForceProtocol [24] similar to other two, it provides blockchain based gaming solutions.

4.4 Development of an example game

We tried to develop a sample game which will have virtual assets that can be incentivize using blockchain technology. This application helped us point out some of the security challenges that a developer has to face for such kind of development. We used Unity3d [27] platform to create this game. With plugin provided by Unity3d we needed not to learn blobkchain programming language.

Chapter 5

Experiments and Results

5.1 Development Environment

Our basic goal is to understand the implementation around virtual items which can be traded over blockchain based environment and to get the hint of how these things work. In future this game can be made online and then more security risk can be identified. Our experimental game contains virtual item that can be traded. By developing this type of game, we can look into the implementational challenges a developer face while making this sort of game.

The environment we pick is Unity3d [27] Gaming engine. Because it is cross platform and a famous powerful gaming engine as well.

DMarket Platform [28] is used for our trading platform to make virtual items trade-able. The reason to use this platform is that it is free and there is a lot of documentation available on how to use this to make a blockchain based video game.

5.2 Gaming Engine

Unity3d, [27] is quite powerful multi-platform gaming engine. The development is done through C# programming language.

5.3 Blockchain based Platform

DMarket, [28] platform provides the feature of buying, selling, exchanging and collecting in-game items. Its freely provided SDK is integrate-able with Unity3d gaming engine. Which

makes in-game virtual items to be trade-able on their platform. DMarket provides an SDK which is free to use and easy to integrate.

5.4 Implementation

Implementation for game which has in-game items that can be used to trade in a blockchain based platform, there are some steps required before coding the game itself, which includes Developer Registration, Game Tokens and API registration etc. All the procedure to develop the game is followed by instruction provided by DMarket free to use plugin instructions

5.4.1 Developer Registration

In order to use DMarket feature, first it is required to register the game with DMarket, which their team does so upon simple email request.

5.4.2 In Game Item Classes

After successful integration JSON text file is needed to be sent to the team including information about virtual items. The JSON format looks like

```
"id": "Unique_ID",
"meta": {
"tile": "GameTile",
"images": [
{
"image": "Image name of virtual item",
"type": "Type of item"
} ],
"category": "Common",
"description": ""
}
}
```

Additionally all items images must be in .png format and archived. Then this archive is sent to DMarket team along with JSON file.

5.4.3 Game Token

Once DMarket team receives items list, they generate a Game Token.

5.4.4 Mobile Game Client and Market Interaction Flow

Following is flow chart representing how mobile game client and DMarket's market interact.

5.4.5 Interaction Flow

Player will start a game session, will collect virtual item. Then will quit the session and will access Game Inventory. Player will be able to register or login to DMarket from here. Player will need to perform authorization through email. After that there can be two cases either Player will have no item or at least one item on DMarket side.

NO ITEMS ON DMARKET YET In this case there won't be sync feature after going back to the game but when user enters or leaves the in-game inventory there will be sync function to DMarket and vice-versa.

ONE OR MORE ITEMS ON DMARKET In this case game will be synced with DMarket account by transferring all items and adding them to inventory inside the game. Game will sync whenever player will enter or refresh the game to add items to game inventory from DMarket and to DMarket from in-game inventory.

5.4.6 DMarket SDK API Clients

There are two kinds of APIs available in provided SDK. ServerAPI and Client API.

ServerAPI ServerAPI communicates with data on game's server side.

ClientAPI ClientAPI communicates with data on game's client side.

Both will be required to setup in the project and additionally server API would require game token to be added to the code.

5.4.7 Basic Access Token

Basic access token is the authorization key for a specific game and user. It can be obtained by making a call to Server API. Basic access token is taken from Server API and is transferred to Client API for initialization purpose. Player can only log-in after initialization.

Fig. 5.1 Flow Chart representation of interaction between mobile game client & DMarket platform

5.4.8 Market Access Token

Market Access Token is necessary in order to send and receive virtual items to and from DMarket platform and player's in-game inventory list. It is used to ensure player's authorization with DMarket.

5.4.9 Inventory List

After player is authorized, a game server can get an inventory list of virtual items which player owns.

5.4.10 Sending & receiving virtual Assets

There are two kind of item transfer features available.

Regular used to get an item from DMarket platform.

Async used to get group of items from DMarket platform.

In response to these call there can be two kind of callbacks from server

Successful sync was successful

Error Error occurred during sync

5.5 Results of Experiment

Above mentioned steps allow video games developers to be able to make virtual items inside the game play to be available in the DMarket platform, from where these can be sold between different players. This implementation bring real monetary value to the virtual assets and both player and developer earn per item

Through these implementation based details we can assume it takes quite an experience from developer side to understand APIs and authorization tasks.

DMarket guarantees the security of their platform as all the security is provided by blockchain's secure structure itself. As one of the DMarket's selling pitch is "Secure payments between users: blockchain leaves no room for fraud and developers can monetize with confidence" [28]

So currently there is no question about how secure the platform will be but this scenario gives rise to another kind of question, such as "what if user's account get hacked?" All of

one player's hard earned assets can be cashed by another person as his virtual items now will belong to someone who does not own them. We discuss this further in next chapter.

Chapter 6

Evaluation and Discussion

6.1 Experimental Game Evaluation

After developing this sample game, we realize that although the blockchain technology is very secure and games based on this technology need not to worry about transactions of in-game virtual items. But the game itself needs to be very secure. The evaluation of experimental game also provides answer to our research question.

6.2 Main Findings

6.2.1 First Question

What challenges games developers face if they shift to blockchain based online games?

While developing the blockchain based games, developers need to be more strict about game play logic, game rules and most importantly no cheat code can be allowed in such kind of games. Because the items the player will earn now will be worth of actual amount and possibility of any kind of cheating will make the room for illegitimate activities.

There is not much but some research work done on how to make online games secure from hacks and cheating, which can be followed to make relevantly secure games. Some important point to be noted are as:

Collaborative approach [4] suggested the data crypto communication mechanism must be developed through the symmetric secret key algorithm and asymmetric secret key algorithm collaborative approach. The authors also designed a model of secure games in which data is transmitted in crypto manner.

Peer to Peer in-game items trading system In order to exchange in-game virtual items fairly and with no duplication, In their work in [12] authors have developed a protocol to solve the problem of secure, peer-to-peer trading in games. The idea of Peer-to-Peer trading has been researched [12] in this article to allow secure trading to virtual items in the game. As blockchain is already peer-to-peer and combination of their protocol inside game and blockchain's peer to peer technology, the trading of virtual items will be relevantly secure.

Common Counter Measures In their work [4] authors advice the game operators to be concerned about common countermeasures that include anti-cheating mechanisms, security detection mechanisms and security management mechanisms. According to authors [4], anti-cheating mechanism can be applied by checking user's identity and doing data transmission in crypto manner. Security detection can be applied to detect abnormality in the games.

Furthermore, mechanism of security management includes users' security management and the operators' security management. "On the one hand, players' awareness on security and anti-stealing should be improved. On the other hand, to avoid stealing and message missing, the operators' interior data management systems should also be improved." [4]

Game Play Logic Security As online computer games are client server based, client sends the data to server whenever there is change of state in the game. According to [5] client side logic validation is a must, which means server must validate the data coming from client side. The data from client side is always assumed to be trust-less. Hence the client requests needed to be validated including some important game data such as AI, skills, articles, trading, etc.

Game Play Rules Being games developers we also advice that game's rules need to be very clear and precise. Any ambiguity in a complex situation can give rise to a situation of abusing game play rules such as in a situation where a player can earn an item by an illegitimate shortcut and without having to actual work for it. This can impose bad effect on the players who follow rules.

6.2.2 Second Question

Possible cyber security concerns with blockchain based online multiplayer games? Even if the games adopt blockchain technology there is still chance of at least three kind of security threats

Cheating Research work in [29], [30] has suggested that cheating is a major new security concern for online computer games. If there are vulnerabilities inside the game logic, it will be easy to cheat and some players will be able to obtain the virtual items which they never earned rightfully. Additionally there are other forms of cheating described in [9] and [7] are as follows.

Plug-in Softwares

Bug Attacks

Co-operation Cheating

Password Stealing

Hacking Once the in-game virtual item contain a monetary value, the security threats are more bothersome as hacking now will cause more serious loss than before. With traditional online gaming, a hacked game situation causes more effect to gaming company because their reputation is degraded and they could lose their registered players.

But with blockchain based gaming, virtual items has worth for both players and developers and now players could lose their items worth of actual money and these kind of hacking will cost actual loss to not only developer but the players as well.

Frauds This situation also gives rise to new frauds related to games. The fraudulent entities will try to lure in the players to share their accounts passwords by posing as representative of gaming company itself. For example if one player has assets worth of good amount, fraudsters can contact them by email or call stating that "As they are producing good revenue for the company, they are eligible for "Gold membership program" and new bonus token. With this upgrade their assets will be doubled in amount."

Then they can ask for password as to upgrade the membership company needs it. Or in some conditions they can pose as company is upgrading whole system and needs the credentials to the accounts in order to verify each players account.

These kinds of frauds are often called "Cheating by Social Engineering" [9]. Any player can fall for that and can lose their account to these frauds.

There are more cheating mechanism discussed in detail in research work done by [9] and blockchain based games can also being cheated in one of these ways. Then calling the blockchain based games secure can be questionable.

6.3 Discussion

Video games development companies or operators are always concerned with cyber security threats they face and are always working very hard to avoid these concerns as much as possible. But it is a fact that cheating in online games is never very hard because of not much attention being paid in this field and there is no hard penalty for such criminals. There are no clear laws whatsoever for players who cheat in the game. For some people it does not seem much of a big offense but companies lose their trust of players and face downfall in registered users which brings loss to the business.

Additionally, Some cyber security specialists and forensics analysts do not consider security and cyber threats in video gaming as serious security concern [7]. But gaming industry is an ever growing multi-billion industry. A massively multiplayer online game serves hundreds and thousands of players at once, with millions of registered players. For instance [30], Sony's massively multiplayer role-playing game earns the company around \$5 million per month only from its monthly subscription fee. In games like this, any security breach can cause the company the loss of multi-million users and degrade its subscribed users count. The reputation of gaming company is at stake and if many players find it easy to breach the security of games then, legitimate players lose interest in the game and hence drop in subscribed users is faced by company.

With blockchain based gaming this poses more threat as now any cheating or hack is more bothersome than before. Blockchain will provide secure way to trade in-game virtual items but games need to be secured from cheating, hacking and frauds.

Chapter 7

Conclusions and Future Work

7.1 Conclusion

It is a fact that blockchain is being adopted in the online gaming industry and everyone is rushing into combination of these two field. Although there have been no case of fraud in this particular field until now only because this is very new field and very little games are implemented that provide this integration and not many people are at the moment playing these games. But there is a huge potential as soon it is going to be as much big industry as online multiplayer games without blockchain.[17]. Now is the time for companies to realize the possible security threats that may arise when blockchain is integrated into online multiplayer games.

Through our work we tried to discover some of these security related issues. Our main concern was to think around the possibility of security threats, after blockchain technology is adopted in online multiplayer video games and through out we tried to bring new security questions, for example.

1. Are the online games secure now and if not what are new security threats?
2. Blockchain promises secure infrastructure but how does vulnerabilities in the game structure itself effect the blockchain based online multiplayer games?
3. What if hacker is able to hack the game and increase the virtual assets to cash-out through crypto-currency?

To explore the possibilities of these scenarios, we developed a sample game to understand implementation-al complexities of such games. This implementation helped us in some ways to understand and answer our first research question. Through this implementation we found that putting the in game virtual assets to blockchain based market is do-able task for indie developers and there are platforms such as [28], [26], [25] available for that. But our conclusion is that if these developers leave any hole or vulnerability in the game logic or structure, it will be more bothersome than before.

Second question was understood through research work and online gaming blogs. Unfortunately, as blockchain technology is considered to be relevantly much secure, games based on it are also considered secure in terms of in-game virtual assets transactions and we did not found any formal research paper which addresses these issues. On the other hand online blogs and articles such as [31], [32] and [18] provide insight on technical and security issues of integration of this two infrastructures.

According to [25] and [26], integration of these two fields provides the most secure games and handling and transaction of in-game assets is very secure through blockchain. [14] is one of the kind research paper that provides some insight on how blockchain effects gamification but still security issues are not addressed that clearly.

Additionally in this work we tried to establish the fact how games can produce real capital for all players through blockchain integration in games and once there is possibility if financial gain in game-play, there is possibility if illicit activities to abuse the features that provide this capital to players.

Through our work we tried to establish the fact that the integration of blockchain technology in online multiplayer games will give rise to new security threats. This in fact opens up new area for cyber security research to find potential threats in blockchain based online games.

7.2 Future Work

Possibility of Future Multiplayer Game Our current implementation is a solo online game in its current state. In future there is possibility of more research on this topic by implementing a game that is an online multiplayer game. This way more security related issues in implementation of these kind of games can be explored.

A honey-pot game As discussed earlier in this dissertation, any vulnerability in game's infrastructure will never cover for security of blockchain technology. Implementation of such game which works as honey pot and contains vulnerabilities in its structure, can be developed to attract hackers and explore how our research questions reflect the real life scenario

Any breakthrough in security research of blockchain technology Additionally any new exploration in security related issues of blockchain technology will bring out new questions in blockchain based gaming as well. As security threat of blockchain will directly effect the games based on this technology.

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Appendix A

How to integrate DMarket Plugin With Unity3D

Unity3d gaming engine is freely available on its site and can be downloaded easily. Integrating DMarket with Unity3d requires to follow specific instructions.

Following instructions are adopted from DMarket plugin integration documentation.

Installing SDK

DMarket SDK is available at Unity Assets Store [27]. Setting up the SDK requires

1. From inside the Unity Editor. Go to asset store window and search DMarket sdk and download and import it.
2. After successful import, start implementation of the package. By default, all folders and items are ticked.
3. After a first stage of importing you see a modal window with available folders. Click "Import" in a bottom right corner to finalize importing.

Integrating SDK

1. Open "Prefabs" Folder
2. Open "UI" Folder
3. In "UI" folder you will find "BasicWidget" item

Fig. A.1 Unity Assets Store

Fig. A.2 Importing DMarket SDK

Fig. A.3 Finalize Importing DMarket SDK

Fig. A.4 Prefabs folder

Fig. A.5 UI folder

Fig. A.6 BasicWidget

Fig. A.7 BasicWidget in Scene

4. Open your project and move "BasicWidget" item to a specific Scene.
5. Add class name and class type "[SerializeField]"
You can also move "BasicWidget" to "Resources folder" and use "Resource.Load(Path)" and then "GameObject.Instance".
6. Click "BasicWidget" to open elements tree. In a "View" folder you can find "FormsRoot" folder which contains list of available functions and elements, such as:

LoginForm

RegisterForm

LoggedForm

VerifyAccountForm

ConnectionLostForm

Fig. A.8 LoginForm

by clicking on each of these items you can check its properties via Unity's Inspector, which appears in a right column.

For example, let's check "LoginForm" properties:

7. As you can see, "WidgetLoginForm" section contains all elements that will be available for a player on Login screen, such as login and password input fields, error text in case player enters wrong credentials, Sign In and Sign Up buttons. You can access "RegisterForm", "LoggedForm", "VerifyAccountForm", "ConnectionLostForm", in a same way via "Inspector".

Fig. A.9 LoginForm Properties - 1

Fig. A.10 LoginForm Properties - 2

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